

Physical Health Awareness and Academic Outcome of Students: A systematic Review

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Abstract:

“Health is the greatest Wealth” it implies the idea of being well, physical as well as mental health. It calls a student healthy when he/she performs well physically as well as mentally. Health awareness is a process of enabling student to increase the control over, and to improve, their health. Day to day habits also determine fitness level of students especially of food, water air all helps in building fitness level of students that effect their academic outcome. Present reviews try to find out the relationship between physical health awareness and academic outcome of high school students. A literature search using J-Gate, Google Scholar, review Science Direct, Research gate, Academia, a data base covering the period from 2000-2022 was conducted. The author reviewed studies with certain inclusion and exclusion criteria. Search terms were Physical health awareness and, Academic outcome of high school students. After examining different types of empirical papers it was found that in most of the studies this variable (Physical Health Awareness) has been ignored by the researchers working this area of research in India. Methodological and theoretical issues have been discussed.

Keywords: physical health awareness, academic outcome, gender, school management, home environment.

Introduction

Health: “Health is a neglected topic until, it is lost.” Ancient view: “sound mind in a sound body, in sound family in a sound environment.” This definition emphasizes on promotion and protection of health. Health is a fundamental human right, it is a integral part of development, and in present time it becomes worldwide social goal. According to Indian Ayurveda and Greek, “being at peace with the Self, the Community, God and Cosmos. In some culture health and harmony are considered equivalent.

Ecological concept- Health is dynamic equilibrium between man and his environment and disease is maladjustment of the human organism to environment.

Holistic concept- It organizes the strength of social economic political and environmental influences on health. Health is a state of complete physical mental and social wellbeing and not merely an absence of disease or infirmity. It is a state in which to be able to lead a socially and economically productive life.

Psychosocial concept- It is not only biomedical phenomenon, but one which is influenced by social, psychological, cultural economic and political factors of the people concerned.

Method for Review -

Literature Search Procedure:

Studies were identified through J- store, Research Gate, Google Scholar, Science Direct. It covers the period from 2000 to 2022. The review is conducted

using the search term Physical Health Awareness, Academic Outcome.

Inclusion Criteria:

Following are the inclusion criteria: (1) empirical studies from peer reviewed journals (2) empirical studies in English language only (3) quantitative research (4) critical review article published in a peer reviewed journal.

Exclusion Criteria

Following are exclusion criteria: (1) Review before 2000 (2) Students from Primary and University.

Methodology

The present review is based on the following six parameters. (1) Research Design: (2) Validity of Criterion variable: (3) Reliability coefficient of predictor variable: (4) Validity and reliability coefficient of different predictor measures on own data: Statistical analysis: (6) Effect size.

Methodology of review studies

All studies are based on Correlation research design all the 100% (25) reviewed studies reported the validity coefficient of criterion measures on their own data in addition, 100% (25) reported the validity reliability coefficient of criterion measures on their own data. 100% (25) reviewed studies reported validity or reliability coefficient of different predictor measures on own data. Further, 100% (25) reviewed studies controlled confounding variables by statistical analysis. Moreover, 100% (25) reviewed studies reported effect size.

Table No. 1 Reviewed Studies

S. No	Title	Source	Author/ Authors	Research Design	Statistical Analysis	Sample Size	Results
1.	Health and fitness awareness in schools and students impact; A Qualitative Study.	https://doi.org/10.33015/dominican.edu/2013.edu.27	Tepas , M.M. 2013	correlation	T Test	150	the students' knowledge about health and fitness is higher in school that provide education on that subject than the schools do not.
2.	Health awareness of high school students	Indian Journal of Community Medicine Education, 32(3), doi: 10.4203/0970-0218.36825	Goel, S. & Singh, A.	Correlation	%	76 students	Various wrong practices and myths associated with illness and injuries have been reported among students.
3.	Health promoting school in India: Approaches and challenges.	J Family Med Prim Care. 2019 Oct, 8(10): 3114-3119.doi: 104103/jfmpc_673_19	Jain,Y.K . & et al..	Correlation	-	Secondary source	There is dire need to develop such model and frameworks that can be replicable to different diverse area of the country.
4.	A Study on Impact of Health Awareness In Education	Journal of Management Research and Analysis, 6, 1(2). pp 135-140, 2019. Doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15470.33607	Sinha, R. & Sinha, K.K.	Correlation	-	Secondary sources	students spur to boost up their daily nutrition intake with proper information and maintain hygiene in their lifestyle.
5.	Intensity of Physical Activity among School going Adolescents in Chennai South India.	International Journal of Community Medicine5(5), 2018.	Balaji, S. M. et al.	Correlation	%	235	Significance relationship between physical activity and reducing the academic stress.
6.	Health Promoting Schools in India: The Time Has Come	Indian Pediatrics. 59, 2022. PII: S0974775591600467	Harish, R. & Pande, D.	Correlation	review	Secondary sources	Age appropriate, health awareness and skills related activities should be essential.
7.	Adherence to components of Health promoting Schools in schools of Bengaluru, India.	Health promotion International, 34(60,2019. https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/day082	Periyasamy, S. & et al. 2019	Correlation	%	61	80% and above schools had proper washrooms for girls and boys, drinking water and ventilation.
8.	School Health program: An Indispensable Program in Child Health	Women and Child (2019) Health1(5),01-10	Obeagu, G. U. & Obeagu, E. I.	Correlation	Review	Secondary sources	Discovered, an indispensable tool for students health to achieve maximum benefit from educational program.
9.	Health promoting schools in Kerala, India.	Indian journal of community medicine, 2019S38-S49. Doi; 0.4103/ijcm.IJC M_31_19	Joseph, P & et al.	Correlation	%	120 schools	Significantly related with academic achievement with respect of public or private schools.

10.	Impact of Physical Education curriculum on Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Schools in India.	International Journal of Physical Education Fitness and Sports. 2023.	Bhowmi ck, S & et al.	Correlatio n	t- Test	180	Significantly related with academic achievement.
11.	Effects of Physical exercise on physical Fitness and mental health of Obese Students.	Journal of Environment and Public Health. 2022. Article-2347205.	Wu, J.	Correlatio n	%	588	Significantly boys are more motivated to participate in physical exercise than girls.
12.	Importance of Physical Fitness in human Development.	International Journal of Recent Research Aspects. ISSN:2349-7688.	Goel, M. et al.	Correlatio n	review	Second ary sources	Physical fitness is significantly related to active and healthy life style.
13.	Physical activity and fitness patterns	International Journal of Advance Research, Ideas and Innovations in Technology	Jambusa ria, S. & et al	Correlatio n	Descripti ve statistics	122	Physical activity and fitness patterns significantly related.
14.	The level of physical Activity and Fitness	International Joint Conference on Arts and Hamanities.(2020)	Nurhasa n, & et al.	Correlatio n	%	490	Musculoskeletal in male and cardiorespiratory in female need to improve.
15.	Health A awareness and study performance in Public educational type Sports Schools.	Central European journal of educational Research. 2021. 3(1), 134-136.	Kalman, K.	Correlatio n	review	Second ary sources	Significant relationship between academic performance and health awareness of students.
16.	Role of Health Education on Awareness and Physical Health of Socially Deprived Students of Islamabad.	Sci.Int(Lahore).2 8(6),171-173,2016. ISSN 1013-5316:CODEN:SI NTE8	Zahra, S. T. & et al.	Correlatio n	SPSS 16	30	Provided evidences for effectiveness of physical health promotion and well being of students.
17.	A Comparative Study of Physical Health Awareness among School Students.	International Journal of Educational Research Studies.2016, I(V),	Prakash, V.	Correlatio n	t-Test descripti ve	200	Significance difference on their physical health awareness boys and girls government schools
18.	The Relationship between Health Awareness and Academic Achievement on a National Representative Sample.	Hungarian Educational Research Journal, 8 (4) 2018.	Kovacs, K. E.	Correlatio n	Regressi on	3015	Significant relationship between health awareness and all subjects, and moderate correlation with a subjective academic achievement.
19.	Health Awareness, Motor performance and Physical Activity of Female students.	Biomedical human Kinetics,4(5): 12-17.(2012)	Konczos , C.	Correlatio n	U Mann Whitney test.	109	Significant relationship between education and healthy behavior.
20.	Physical Activity and	Pandolfo, et al.	Pandolfo		Regressi	348	Sports activities beneficial

	Academic Performance in High School Students	Rev Bras Fis Saude. 2017;22(5):486-92	,K. C. M. & et al.	correlation	on		in students' cognitive performances.
.21	The relationship between Physical Fitness and Academic Achievement in Physical Education, Sports and Health	International Conference on Sports and Science. 2018, pp-124-128, ISBN:978-989-758-317-9	Bayu, W. & Hasmara, P.	correlation	Descriptive statistics	36	Significant relationship between health fitness and academic achievement.
22.	Health, Academic Achievement and School-Based Intervention	Open access peer reviewed chapter, 2018. Doi:10.5772?intechopen.76431.	Matingwina, T.	correlation	Descriptive statistics	Secondary sources	Develop integrated health intervention effectiveness related with promoting healthy life style among students.
23	Effects of Health related Physical Education on Academic Achievement: SPARK	The American Alliance for Health, Physical Education, Recreation and Dance, 70(2), pp. 127-134.	Sallis, J. F. & et al.	correlation	Cohort retention	1538	Physical activity significantly related to good physical mental health and academic achievement.
24.	Effect of Physical Education Intervention on Academic Performance: A Cluster Randomized Controlled trial	International journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. 17(4287):4287 (2020)	Lima, R. & et al.	Correlation	ANOVA	1200	Significantly interventions are not effective in improving the students' academic achievement.
25.	Impacting Children's health and Academic Performance through Comprehensive School Physical Activity programming	International Electronic journal of elementary education. 2015, 7(3), 441-450.	Brusseau, T.A. & Hannon, J.C.	Correlation	Regression	Secondary sources	With little planning and commitment from all school administrators and staff members has to make improvement at very low cost.

Table No. 2 Methodological Assessment of Reviewed Studies

Studies		Years	Parameters					
S. No.	Authors		Research Design	Validity of Criterion Variable	Reliability Coefficient of Predictor Variable	Validity and Reliability Coefficient of Different Predictor Measure on Own Data	Statistical Analysis	Effect Size
1.	Tepas, M.M.	2013	0	1	1	1	1	1
2.	Goel, S & Singh, A.	2007	0	1	1	1	1	1
3.	Jain, Y.K. & et al.	2019	0	1	1	1	1	1
4.	Sinha, R. & Sinha, K. K.	2019	1	1	1	1	1	1
5.	Balaji, S.M.	2018	0	1	1	1	1	1
6.	Harish, R. & Pande, D.	2022	0	1	1	1	1	1
7.	Periyasamy, S. & el al.	2019	0	1	1	1	1	1
8.	Obeagu, G.U. & Obeagu, E.I.	2019	0	1	1	1	0	1

9.	Joseph, P. & et al.	2019	0	1	1	1	1	1
10.	Bhowmick, S. & et al.	2023	0	1	1	1	1	1
11.	Wu, J.	2022	0	1	1	1	1	1
12.	Goel, M. et al.	2014	0	1	1	1	1	1
13.	Jambusariya, S. & et al.	2020	0	1	1	1	1	1
14.	Nurhasan, & et al.	2020	0	1	1	1	1	1
15.	Kalman, K.	2021	0	1	1	1	0	1
16.	Zahra, S.T. & et al.	2016	0	1	1	1	1	1
17.	Prakash, V.	2016	0	1	1	1	1	1
18.	Kovacs, K. E.	2018	0	1	1	1	1	1
19.	Konczos, C.	2012	0	1	1	1	1	1
20.	Pandolfo, K.C.M. et al.	2018	0	1	1	1	1	1
21.	Bayu, W. and Hasmara, P.	2017	0	1	1	1	1	1
22.	Matingwina, T.	2018	0	1	1	1	1	1
23.	Sallis, J.F. & et al.	2000	0	1	1	1	1	1
24.	Lima, R. & et al.	2020	0	1	1	1	1	1
25.	Brusseau, T. A.&Hannon, J.C.	2014	0	1	1	1	1	1

Scoring pattern: Scoring patterns suggested by Kamal, Tiwari, Behera & Hasan (2018), Tiwari et al. (2017), Khan & Hasan (2016), Shukla, Hasan, Mitra (2018). Research design (longitudinal=1, Cross sectional= 0), validity coefficient of criterion measure on own data (yes=1, No=0), reliability coefficient of criterion measure on own data (yes=1, No=0), validity or reliability coefficient of different predictor measure (yes=1, No=0), statistical analysis viz-controlling of confounding variables (yes=1, No=0), and reported effect size(yes=1, No=0).

Discussion

Physical health awareness not only changes body, it changes mind, attitude and mood. The result revealed that it is significant predictor of academic outcome of high school students. It is positively related to variables like food habit, life style, playing games and exercises, psychosocial factors, emotional intelligence, physical activity, prosocial behavior, cognitive abilities etc. The research studies employed simple random technique, while some other studies employed stratified area and incidental cum random sampling techniques. Most studies used various statistical analysis techniques like t-Test, ANOVA, descriptive analysis, standard deviation, Percentage, multiple regression analysis, multi variable analysis. Reviewed studies employed cross sectional research design, that are provide evidences regarding the degree of relationship among factors and the degree of relationship among factors and causal relationship among factors. Several reviewed studies controlled confounding variables by different statistical analysis. Reviewed studies reported effect size. Studies also revealed that there is statistically yet small gender differences in physical activities in girl and boy students, where girls show more shy and taking interest in household chores and boy students like playing games of more kinds and other activities.

Conclusion:

“It is health which is real wealth and not pieces of gold and silver” (M.K. Gandhi). This review paper gives vivid view on various psychological and social factors that link the relation between physical health awareness and personality of student and both impact on academic outcome of school student. It also analyzes the need to include health awareness and promotion in schools in order to educate the students and their parents about fitness and food health. The growing trends of child obesity, physical inactivity and the resulting health factors encourage to promote the need of physical health awareness. The findings of the studies show, some literature on the topic of obesity and diabetes centers on the definitions of obesity, diabetes and obesity, education for youth and fitness, actions taken in schools to improve physical activity and nutrition. Finally, this paper also considers the importance of the relationship between physical health awareness and fitness and adds to existing studies by showing results that support the idea that students’ knowledge base on health related issues can significantly grow when exposed to educational lessons and sessions.

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